

Gimme! Gimme! Gimme! (A Reliable Access Method for ChatGPT in Archaeological Heritage Prompting)

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Abstract

This paper evaluated ChatGPT – specifically the 4o model – as a source of knowledge on archaeological heritage and memory sites. The authors argue a need for assessing the different platforms used to access a singular generative AI model. Two case studies were used to investigate the proposed subject, two categories that are trending in current research: heritage tourism and contested heritage. The goal was to determine differences in responses from ChatGPT-4o prompted using different platforms to investigate and generate outcomes of archaeological heritage information, highlighting the advantages and disadvantages. Understanding different narratives constructed by a singular model across different platforms provides insight into both the interpretations presented to users and potential inversion of democratising knowledge. A mixed-methodological approach employing qualitative interpretations using critical heritage perspectives, paired with an exploratory analysis using Topic Modelling was applied to multiple corpora of generated responses. Results indicated differences in constructed narratives between platforms, with a clear hierarchy in the language and content present. Calling to attention a need to address the potential of generative AI models contributing to the monopolization of knowledge in the contexts of heritage tourism and contested heritage.

Keywords: Generative AI, Textual Analysis, ChatGPT, Heritage Tourism, Contested Heritage, Archaeological Landscapes

1. Introduction

Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) models have been substantially integrated into daily life, with users embodying diverse expertise and topics of interest. Additionally, access to specific platforms influence both usage and the information generated. Focusing on ChatGPT particularly, its usage is well-documented from both a general perspective, which highlighted impacts on education, work and cultural representations, and a broad lens focused on concepts such as ethics, language and digital rights (Konstantinos and Lambrou, 2023; Zirar, 2023; Isiaku *et al.*, 2024). Previous research into ChatGPT – and similar models – have revealed the types of biases that are often reproduced within generated outputs, reflecting and occasionally amplifying social, political and gender inequalities present within the training data (Abid, Farooqi & Zou 2021; Munn, Magee & Arora 2023). These studies further revealed limitations of supposed ‘algorithmic neutrality’ while actively contributing to a wider debate on the governance and transparency of generative AI.

The rapid proliferation of generative AI models, prominent examples include DeepSeek and Gemini, has prompted an increase of comparative studies with research centred on the evaluation of output quality, readability and effectiveness across varying models (Aydin *et al.*, 2025). Though, an equally relevant aspect has so far gone unexplored: is there a substantial difference in outputs stemming from the same generative AI model when accessed from a different platform? Even if the underlying model is the same, implementation varies depending on the interface or platform selected, accessibility influencing the selection of said platform, default settings and the targeted user (Garg & Shaikh 2024; Davar, Dewan & Zhang 2025). These variations raise important questions regarding the necessity and role of platform mediation in shaping user experience and narrative output.

This study investigates ChatGPT-4o’s discourse variations across three platforms: [OpenAI](#), [ELM](#) and [Replit](#). Preliminary explorations into utilising these platforms revealed inconsistencies in the responses generated (González Cantera & Bonacchi 2025). The discrepancies uncovered included notable differences in the length of responses and themes addressed, despite using an identical model, presented a need for a closer examination of the platforms themselves. While each response generated by ChatGPT-4o will differ – regardless if the same prompt is repeated, due to the probabilistic ‘next word’ generation structure and settings like ‘temperature’ which influences randomness (Holtzman *et al.* 2020) – the level of differentiation was enough to raise more questions. Therefore, an exploratory analysis was conducted with the following research objectives:

- (a) To identify dominant themes across platforms using Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) applied to generated outputs.
- (b) To determine potential causes of output divergence across platforms using the same model and prompts.

1.1. Research Background

Developed by OpenAI and released in May 2024, ChatGPT 4o is an advanced iteration of the Generative Pretrained Transformer model (Breazu & Katsos 2024), which employs probabilistic modelling to predict word relationships and interpret textual context (Tlili *et al.* 2023, p. 2). Model training approaches evolved to include the incorporation of human feedback (i.e., Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback or RHLF), which has reportedly enhanced the accuracy and relevance of outputs – which is present in the 4o model (Ouyang *et al.* 2022). Comparative studies on the reliability and stability of responses in ChatGPT-4o (Wang *et al.* 2025) showed improvements with the model, which supported its selection as the focal point. Additionally, the technical sophistication and extensive adoption – as by February 2025, it had reached 400 million users worldwide with projections estimating one billion by year’s end (Duarte 2025; Paris 2025) – made it ideal for this specific investigation.

Furthermore, it was possible to prompt the ChatGPT-4o model across three distinct access platforms. Rather than focusing exclusively on the outputs generated by each platform (i.e., inter-platform variability) – by comparing differences in structure and content, it was possible to discern potential ‘knowledge hierarchies’. Within the archaeological heritage context, recognizing any knowledge monopoly is crucial in public understanding of heritage. There is a large array of users interested in this subject that possess different technical skills or even comprehension of these platforms, paired with platforms maintaining different restrictions – this study can provide insight into how a singular generative AI model can provide both advantages and disadvantages in informal learning scenarios.

1.2. ‘Hot Topics’ in Archaeological Heritage

This paper examined responses generated by the ChatGPT-4o model as accessed across different platforms through the lens of two ‘hot topics’ within the fields of Archaeology and Heritage Studies. The designation of ‘hot topics’ is argued by the authors as a way to distinguish current trending subject areas, appealing to both academic researchers and non-specialist members of the public. In addition, we further align our thinking that distinct periods of ‘trending’ themes and topics permeate the academic sphere with generative AI itself a current ‘hot topic’ with similar patterns in influencing both research and discourse (Magnani & Clindaniel 2023; Tenzer *et al.* 2024). Two significant trending ‘hot topics’ – both academically and generally – are heritage tourism and contested heritage. We intended to explore the levels of similarities and differences between generated responses with results interpreted through the lens of the proposed ‘hot topics’ for insight into how each platform deciphers and presents archaeological heritage discourse. Within the rest of the paper, these trending ‘hot topics’ will be referenced as Subject Area 1: Heritage Tourism and Subject Area 2: Contest Heritage for clarity. Beyond evaluating the type of knowledge generated between platforms, focusing on the selected subject areas aligns with current overlap between research into heritage tourism practices and contested discourse.

The relationship between heritage tourism and contested heritage is visible through various interpretations, narratives and contexts placed on surviving heritage. Clear associations between these subject areas present in discourse are economic benefits, political ideologies and heritage consumption practices including discussions grounded in contested heritage sites made accessible for tourism (Silverman 2010; Murtagh, Boland & Shirlow 2017; Zhu 2025). The analyses of the tourist economy post ‘ontological turn’ (Harrison 2018) is relative to discursive patterns of contradicting heritage narratives (Porter 2016) which highlights the need for a deeper examination of the intersection between tourism and contested narratives as accepted authorised heritage discourse (Rellensmann 2024) in which we aim to contribute to this discussion. Factors that contribute to authorised heritage narratives include: shifting political and nationalistic ideologies (Waterton 2013), economic impacts (Hampton 2005), consumerism (Liu, Yang & Su 2023) and engagement practices (Smith 2022) – which presents heritage sites as eligible for tourism practices simultaneous with contestation within both research and social uses. The interwoven nature of these subject areas – that deeply contribute to public understandings of the past in the present – further calls for examinations into how these concepts are presented within generative AI outputs. Evaluating information generated by ChatGPT 4o with this lens provides insight into the relationship between subject areas and acuity of generated archaeological heritage explanations.

Heritage tourism and contested heritage are intertwined in the academic and public spaces, even if there are no overt, specialised studies. These are subjects with significant debates requiring holistic, embodied and inclusive perspectives across authorised and non-authorised discourses (Silverman 2008; Waterton & Watson 2015; Santa & Tiatco 2019). Heritage engagement practices, including tourism endeavours to heritage sites, cultural institutions and archaeological landscapes are enmeshed and dependent on narratives supplied to academics and members of the public. Many sites – beyond those discussed in this paper – are grounded and presented using contested narratives, memories and uses. Whether promoting nationalistic ideologies, political biases or controversial uses – remaining archaeological heritage sites and landscapes intersect in research and practice. The emergence of generative AI models across stakeholders – academic researchers, heritage professionals, local communities, etc. – increases the need for evaluating the presence of narratives and content that users have access to depending on the selected platform and context. We believe it is integral to assess model outputs across various platforms users have access to – in an effort to contribute to debates on generative AI’s ability to democratise archaeological heritage knowledge.

2. Case Study

To examine both the presentation of subject areas within the archaeological heritage context within generative AI outputs and variability between platforms, we carried out an exploratory study on three platforms: OpenAI, ELM and Replit. These platforms were the case studies to analyse interface design, user accessibility and technical affordances that could influence potential user experience and discursive characteristics of outputs (Davar, Dewan & Zhang 2025). The reasoning behind this approach is linked to three aspects: usage, structure and impact. More specifically, 1)

Who is using these platforms? 2) What is the interface design of these platforms? and 3) What is the impact on public perception of the archaeological heritage subject areas? Therefore, our selection criteria for platforms considered different interfaces, restrictions, and targeted users. Following the selection process the decision for a platform to platform variability – rather than an inter-platform variability – stemmed from two reasons.

First, we want to present how each platform generates information with a distinct narrative impacting the type of perception one can gain about the subject areas. Particularly, the amount of content and language used provides insight into the potential for ChatGPT-4o – and the respective platforms – to either contribute to the democratisation of knowledge or reinforcing hierarchies. As the information provided will ultimately shape user perception and understandings of heritage tourism and contested heritage. Secondly, we are interested in the variability of responses from the user perspective. There are OpenAI, ELM and Replit users with various interests, technical understandings of LLM's and access. With debates predominately situated in choosing models (i.e., comparisons between ChatGPT, Gemini, or Copilot) we are curious to what extent users consider the impact of selecting a specific access method. Rather than just considering a model, considering the platform should be part of discussions on veracity, content and access.

Beginning with OpenAI, this is a US-based artificial intelligence organisation established in 2015, recognised for developing the ChatGPT platform (Fitria 2023). The platform functions as a web-based application, allowing user interaction with OpenAI's language models – including GPT-4o – through a conversational, user-friendly interface. Designed with an emphasis on accessibility, it is particularly suited to a general, non-specialist audience. Consequently, the responses generated via OpenAI tend to be broad in scope and relatively basic in content, reflecting its orientation towards widespread public engagement. While OpenAI is 'openly accessible' to a wide audience, it is not 'open source' as there are restrictions with message caps and limited free access to the most advanced model. Even so, this platform can be considered the most widely-utilised platform – in comparison to the two other platforms within this study.

Continuing with ELM, or 'the Edinburgh (access to) Language Models, is a platform developed and managed by the University of Edinburgh. ELM offers a more restricted, academically curated environment for accessing language models. Access is restricted to the university community, including students and staff, with the primary intention for education and research. This controlled framework facilitates a secure and pedagogically informed engagement with generative AI, encouraging its responsible use within academic settings. In addition, user data is securely managed and not utilised by third-party services for training models or any other external purposes (University of Edinburgh 2024).

By contrast, Replit is a widely used collaborative programming platform that configures development environments, manages API requests/responses and creates user interfaces to support interactions with AI models (Garg & Shaikh 2024). While this access method has less restrictions

than ELM (i.e., not being exclusive to a specific university community) and OpenAI (i.e., paywall hierarchy) – there is a degree of technical proficiency, or at least comfortability, when using this platform as Replit maintains less of a ‘chatbot’ feel. As a result, this platform is most suitable for users with prior experience in programming who seek greater control over the input–output process (Lokare & Jadhav 2024). The responses generated tend to be concise and specific, reflecting the structured and code-based nature of its interaction framework.

2.1 Classification of Results

Previous research centred on exploring archaeological heritage and generative AI has identified both potential use and issues. Previous research includes projects examining tools to generate 3D reconstructions of artefacts (Altaweel & Khelifi 2024) and sites (Cobb 2023), characterising visitors for embodied tourism experiences (Schrader *et al.* 2025) and best practices for heritage engagement with cultural institutions (Spennemann 2025). This research appears along critical assessments of the impact generative AI may have on archaeological heritage research development (Spennemann 2023), ability to participate in intricate heritage discourse debates (Menotti 2025) and ethical repercussions linked to authenticity and credibility (Munn, Magee & Arora 2023). Results from these projects fortified a lens of thinking – beyond positives and negatives of using generative AI for archaeological heritage – to focus exclusively on a specific platform’s role in influencing generated responses.

Within this study we aimed to develop a classification system to act as the interpretive lens of the responses generated. Presented in **Table 1** below, we are proposing our preliminary classification scheme that was used to frame generated responses for the analysis of platforms influencing user experience and outputs of archaeological heritage information. The goal was for insight beyond the impact of generative AI models within archaeological heritage research grounded in the generated themes, biases and dominant narratives at a secondary level: access platforms. Our classification scheme is focused on three concepts: complexity, accessibility and type of information.

	OpenAI	ELM	Replit
Complexity	How complex is each respective platform in prompting using the ChatGPT 4o model? Does the required level of prompting skill vary across platforms when using ChatGPT 4o?		
Accessibility	What is the level of accessibility for general users when using each platform? Are there differences in user interface that affect accessibility?		
Type of Information	What type of information is the ChatGPT 4o model capable of generating per each platform? What level of customisation is offered to users on different platforms?		

Table 1. Classification factors of results

Starting with complexity, this is in reference to both the level of complexity of usage and generated responses. Regarding the usage, the classification of complexity is linked with how digitally literate a user needs to be based on the targeted user and how complex it is to actually run a prompt and review the response. As far as the generated response itself, how complex are the responses. Are the generated responses succinct and easily understood by non-experts, or do responses contain more specialized language and explanations. Continuing with accessibility this is grounded on how user-friendly is the platform and what are in the restrictions of each platform. Are there restrictions of access based on finances or intended users. Concluding with types of information, this is relative to the narratives and context generated information is rooted within, when presented as a response. Based on the information generated between each platform, what are the unique capabilities and can the variability impact both past perception and democratising archaeological heritage knowledge.

2.2. Archaeological Heritage Lens

Beginning with Subject Area 1: Heritage Tourism, two archaeological sites within the United Kingdom were selected to discern explanations and interpretations of these sites in line with heritage tourism practices. Previous research investigated individual interests and motivations that inspire heritage engagement practices, such as visiting sites for tourism practices (McGrath, Primm & Lafe 2017), along with decision-making capacities of individuals that guide visits and experiences (Adie & Hall 2017). Two Neolithic Stone Circles in England and Scotland were the chosen sites through which to explore narratives of generated information for users that are interested in coordinating visits to these locations. Continuing with Subject Area 2: Contested Heritage two sites linked to Spanish-speaking dictatorships were examined to determine continued visibility and contestation of these heritage sites within national discourses. Defined by competing interpretations of strong emotional investments rooted in political and social commitments, this form of heritage is shaped by overlapping and often conflicting memories (Liu, Dupre & Jin 2021). Its dynamic nature increases responsiveness to digital public engagements (Bonacchi 2022), where diverse stakeholders – victims’ families, activists, scholars and institutions – negotiate meaning and representation. Selected sites in Spain and Argentina reflect the unresolved legacies of authoritarian rule pervading generative AI.

The first Neolithic Stone Circle monument – Stonehenge – is located in the Salisbury Plain in Wiltshire, England. This site is considered one of the most iconic heritage tourism sites in the United Kingdom and viewed as a symbol of English heritage (English 2002). The bluestones used to construct the monument were raised around 2500 BCE, offering modern people a striking view into prehistoric mobility and engineering (Parker Pearson 2021). Combined with the monuments astronomical alignment, there has been constant interest in the relationship with solstice events and potential uses including a solar calendar for ceremonial events (Darvill 2022). This site has entranced both researchers and tourists alike with its mystery and grandeur, granting Stonehenge a prominent role in landscape archaeology, heritage pedagogy and prehistoric symbolism (Pitts 2009; Darvill 2019; Schwartz 2023). The second Neolithic Stone Circle – Callanish (or Calanais) –

can be found on the Isle of Lewis in Scotland. This site is well-known as the ‘Scottish Stonehenge’ due to the dramatic landscape setting and spiritual atmosphere (Burl 1993, pg. 58-65; Higginbottom 2024). Though predating Stonehenge, Callanish captivates visitors that are interested in a more rural and immersive experience with remains of the Neolithic (Higginbottom & Clay 2016) and complex analyses of surrounding geography (Bates *et al.* 2019). Callanish offers visitors a remote, more intimate connection with both folklore and tourism to the Outer Hebrides (Muir & Richards 2013, pg. 292-300). Both sites are recognized as integral remnants of the Neolithic that have been placed in high-standings within the current modern landscape – with value associated to the monuments themselves, the physical landscape past people placed them within and what these places are capable of offering the public. Stonehenge and Callanish each offer a glimpse into varying perspectives surrounding public perceptions of these sites within the tourism sphere.

In Spain, the Valley of the Fallen – recently renamed the Valley of Cuelgamuros – was constructed under Franco’s regime (1940–1958) using forced labour from Republican prisoners (González Ruibal 2021). Originally conceived as a Spanish Civil War burial site for all affiliations (Encarnación 2017; Solé Barjau & López Soler 2019), many Republican victims were interred without family consent. The site also housed the remains of Franco and José Antonio Primo de Rivera, founder of the Falange, until their exhumations in 2019 and 2021, respectively. Today, the Valley remains a highly contested symbol central to debates on historical memory, reconciliation, and legacy of authoritarianism (Gardiner 2022; Marín Suárez 2022; Sassi 2024). In Argentina, the ESMA Museum and Site of Memory in Buenos Aires contains the most notorious clandestine detention and torture centre used during the last military dictatorship (1976–1983). Since 2004, it has served as a museum dedicated to memorialisation and human rights education (Lessa 2014), with addition to the UNESCO World Heritage List in 2023 recognising its global significance in the struggle against authoritarianism. However, under President Javier Milei, the site faces threats of defunding and possible closure. Recent censorship of a concert by artist Milo J illustrates mounting political pressures facing memory institutions in contemporary Argentina (Altamirano 2025; Caminos 2025).

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Materials

To reiterate, three platforms – OpenAI, ELM and Replit – were used to explore responses generated about archaeological heritage information through the pre-defined lens of complexity, accessibility and type of information that influences interpretations and perceptions of the past. Beyond the platforms themselves, additional materials include both subject areas, individual sets of prompts and generated responses from each platform. Each subject area contains a series of prompts constructed by the research and representing different prompt types. Subject Area 1 comprises five prompts (**Table 2**), whereas Subject Area 2 includes four prompts, presented in **Table 3**. All of these questions refer to both general or basic enquiries about these sites (i.e., what the site is) and for more specific issues concerning them (i.e., controversies surrounding these

spaces). All prompts were queried per platform to generate responses for extraction and analysis. Beyond the platforms, additional software was used to store data – SQLite (Hipp 2020) – that was linked to R 4.4.1 and explored using custom scripts (R Core Team 2024). The storage method and software were selected due to the open-source nature and effectiveness of linking datasets within databases directly to R for data processing, analysis and data visualizations. In total, there were six corpora of generated responses from all platforms were analysed.

	Prompt Type	Prompt
Prompt #1	Instructional	Tell me about Callanish – what to see, features, and best time to visit
Prompt #2	Summarization	Provide a summary of the key features of Stonehenge
Prompt #3	Informational	What experience would I have at Callanish?
Prompt #4	Question and Answering	Is Stonehenge still relevant today and is it's use case still viable for our modern society?
Prompt #5	Comparison	How does Stonehenge compare to other sites around the world, such as Machu Picchu, Easter Island, and Petra?

Table 2. Prompts and respective prompt types used in Subject Area1: Heritage Tourism

	Prompt Type	Prompt
Prompt #1	Informational	What is the Valley of the Fallen?
Prompt #2	Informational	What is the ESMA-Ex Clandestine Detention, Torture and Extermination Centre?
Prompt #3	Summarization	Provide a detailed explanation of the controversies surrounding this monument?
Prompt #4	Question and Answering	How many people died at ESMA-Ex Clandestine Detention, Torture and Extermination Centre?

Table 3. Prompts and respective prompt types used in Subject Area 2: Contested Heritage

3.2. Methods

The analyses were carried out using a mixed-methodological approach employing both quantitative textual analysis, specifically Topic Modelling, paired with a qualitative lens. The goal was to discern usability and efficacy relative to the subject areas to showcase the variability of responses the ChatGPT 4o model generates – depending on the platform. The analyses of variabilities per platform highlight prevalent narratives and contexts of interpreted archaeological heritage subject areas provided to users. Each subject area consists of constructed prompts that

were queried individually in multiple iterations for each platform. For example, the prompt “*What experience would I have at Callanish?*” was submitted 15 times via the OpenAI interface, with each response recorded, and repeated 15 times on each of the other two platforms. The same procedure was applied to the remaining prompts across all three platforms (see **Table 4**). Repeating each question across all platforms enabled us to assess and mitigate platform-specific variability. Fifteen repetitions were selected to capture variation without generating an excessively large corpus.

ChatGPT-4o outputs were obtained through the user interfaces of three platforms, without access to the underlying model parameters or documentation of the generation settings. Users could not control variables such as temperature, sampling seed, or system prompts, and these configurations are not publicly documented. As a result, the platforms function as black-box systems (Schwartz *et al.* 2024: 864). Observed differences in outputs may therefore reflect platform-specific system prompts, differing default parameters, different model snapshots (as OpenAI released multiple GPT-4o versions during 2024), or the inherent stochasticity of probabilistic language models. Moreover, the study does not establish a baseline for expected variation: repeated runs of the same prompt within a single platform may yield different outputs due to sampling variability. Without characterising this baseline, it is not possible to determine whether differences across platforms exceed variation that may occur by chance. Consequently, quantitative comparison between platforms is limited. This study should therefore be interpreted primarily as an exploration of platform experiences, treating each platform as a complete socio-technical system rather than as a direct comparison of model behaviour. Observed differences should not be interpreted as causal, as multiple external factors may influence the results. All corpora analyses were compiled between March and early April 2025 using ChatGPT-4o, the newly released Replit Agent (an AI coding assistant), and the then-current version of ELM, which provided access to the GPT-4o model.

	OpenAI	ELM	Replit
Prompt	15 Iterations	15 Iterations	15 Iterations
Prompt	15 Iterations	15 Iterations	15 Iterations
Prompt	15 Iterations	15 Iterations	15 Iterations
~	~	~	~

Table 4. Example of the research design of prompt iterations applied to each prompt for Subject Area 1 and Subject Area 2

The analytic approach employed in this study was exploratory in nature, using Topic Modelling to investigate emergent patterns within the generated responses rather than to perform formal comparisons. Topic Modelling is a technique designed to uncover latent themes or ‘topics’ within a corpus of texts (Daud *et al.*, 2010; Egger, 2022). In this study, the Latent-Dirichlet Allocation

(LDA) algorithm was selected due to previous success in archaeological heritage research (Chen & Marwick, 2023; Schwartz, Giner & Campillo 2024; Tenzer & Schofield 2024; González Cantera & Bonacchi 2025). LDA is an unsupervised, probabilistic-type of machine learning algorithm for generating topics using term distribution probabilities (Onan, Korukoglu & Bulut 2016). Each corpus underwent a processing chain in the R user interface (see Acknowledgements for R packages used) which involved stopword removal and stemming/lemmatisation. The aim of these procedures was to eliminate redundant or non-informative textual elements that could adversely affect the performance of the algorithm (Jelodar et al. 2019). To ensure reproducibility, random seeds were fixed prior to LDA estimation (42 for Model 1; 314159 for Model 2), guaranteeing identical results under the same computational conditions.

Subsequently, each corpus was transformed to a Document-Term Matrix, or DTM, which is a mathematical representation of textual data in which every row is a text, and each column is a term (Feinerer 2013). A series of metrics testing was run using a Gibbs sampling method (Gao, Chen & Zhu 2016) with results to guide the setting of parameters, including the number of topics the model would search for and minimum frequency (Onan, Korukoglu & Bulut 2016). LDA operates by considering each individual text as a collection of topics, with each topic a distribution of terms. Generated outputs consist of each term assigned a weight for each topic, with each topic weighted per text – with the total number of topics appearing based on parameters (Daud *et al.* 2010). This exploratory approach was applied individually to each corpus, with the aim of identifying patterns that could inform future research directions rather than to perform quantitative comparisons across datasets.

In addition to the quantitative topic modelling, a qualitative analysis was undertaken to provide a more nuanced understanding of the responses generated by the ChatGPT 4o model. This qualitative component functioned as a supplementary lens to the exploratory topic modelling, allowing the study to interpret not only the prevalence of topics but also the meaning, tone, and contextual framing within the generated texts across different platforms. Each iteration of the prompts was read in its entirety, with attention given to the manner in which the text framed these sites, including the use of temporal, spatial, and cultural references, and the balance between factual information and immersive experiential description.

All data and code employed in this study have been deposited in a Zenodo repository to ensure transparency and reproducibility: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17121909>.

4. Results

Outputs are three different LDA models of responses generated within each platform for both subject areas. Regarding Subject Area 1, the OpenAI model contains six topics, while both ELM and Replit have five topics. Continuing with Subject Area 2, all three models contain seven topics. All topics – across the six corpora – contain the top ten terms per topic. Results indicate that while there are clear similarities between the themes in the responses per access platform, there are

differences and variations in responses that highlight the extended uniqueness beyond the model into each platform. The exploratory LDA analysis is further accompanied by a qualitative textual analysis rooted in presented narratives and contexts.

4.1. Subject Area 1: Heritage Tourism

Beginning with OpenAI (**Figure 1**), topics present contain terms that highlight both sites as they are entrenched within heritage tourism narratives, yet there was a clear emphasis on Stonehenge (Topic 1, 3 and 5) when compared to Callanish (Topic 6). Initially indicating a weak presence of Callanish, that could impact generated responses. Even with a Stonehenge-focused lens, additional topics emphasize interpretations of these sites through the lens of 'trending' tourism topics, such as emotional stakes, associated events and fortified 'site identities'. For instance, Topic 2 pertains to individuals' feelings and experiences with a site stemming from the history and typology linked to Neolithic monuments in the present landscape (*spiritual, mystical, ancient*). One response from the ChatGPT-4o chatbot via the OpenAI platform was: “*Visiting the ****Callanish Stones**** on the Isle of Lewis in Scotland is like stepping into a mystical, ancient world. Here’s what you could expect from the experience: The stones are set on a scenic hilltop... it always feels powerful and atmospheric ... this is not a crowded touristy place, more of a spiritual, raw encounter with the past...(CAL/ENG/Prompt 3/Response 4)*” The response, with terms that are ‘flowery’ in nature, is rooted in a narrative that is grounded in trendy terminology meant to entice the public through aesthetics and experience linked with presenting a site beyond tourism. Even though the line of questioning is related to tourism, the response explicitly stated this is not a ‘toursity place’ but ‘spiritual’ to be viewed as more appealing to tourists.

OpenAI generated responses had narratives and content more grounded in aesthetic and social heritage values. Information provided is surface-level, sandwiched between buzzwords: “*...Iconic and mysterious ... (STO/ENG/Prompt 5/Response 4)*”, “*... cultural significance...(STO/ENG/Prompt 4/Response 14)*” and “*... ceremonial landscape... (CAL/ENG/Prompt 1/ Response 6)*” – but knowledge presented does not contain historic or technical framing. Topic 4 relates to the oft discussed relationship between Stone Circles – especially Stonehenge and Callanish – to solstice celebrations, heavily discussed in academic research and as a tourism promotion tool (*solstice, features, used*), yet is only briefly mentioned without *why* the alignment with the solstices may be meaningful or the importance of the potential function for past people, “*... Aligns with the summer and winter solstices, indicating a solar calendar function... (STO/ENG/Prompt 2/Response 11)*.” It is fair to assume and present that the alignment could be relative to a solar calendar – but there is a lack of depth into what is meaningful or important about a solar calendar and any potential uses – as said meaning pertains to both past people themselves and modern understandings of past people. Ultimately, the OpenAI model trended in a Stonehenge-centric direction that dominated responses.

Figure 1. LDA results from the OpenAI platform on the heritage tourism topic

Continuing with ELM (**Figure 2**), there is a contextual shift in generated responses situated in academic and technical presentations relative to accepted authorised heritage discourse within research, discernible in linguistic patterns. For example, there is an increase in specificity and technical details seen in Topic 1 with the term *lewis* (i.e., the isle in which Callanish is located) formally associating significance with the physical space and other attributes. Along with new terminology across this corpora, i.e., *significance*, *heritage*, *visitor*, *educational* and *landscape* that ground these responses in narratives that reflect current embodied heritage tourism research. This response from ELM is also from Prompt 3 referenced above, “*Visiting Callanish offers a captivating and atmospheric experience... Gain insights into the history, archaeology, and legends associated with Callanish... Experience the unique culture of the Outer Hebrides, known for its Gaelic heritage... Overall, a visit to Callanish is both enriching and memorable, offering a deeper connection to the ancient past. (CAL/ENG/Prompt 3/Response 8).*” There is still the appearance of trending or engaging terms capable of peaking a users interest, the response actually provides deeper insight into *what* a heritage tourist can engage with and *why* it could be meaningful. The inclusion of references to Gaelic heritage, the Outer Hebrides and cultural connections – can contribute to influencing and shaping public interest in visiting said site. By offering a specific lens into what a tourist could experience. Additionally, there is still a divide in the narratives placed

upon Stonehenge and Callanish in responses that reflect current debates in research and placing the context of current perspectives unique to relationships with these sites. Stonehenge, is linked predominantly with social uses relative to research and astronomical events, whereas Callanish is mainly presented with social uses pertaining to the physical attributes and unifying the monument with the landscape. Within ELM responses, Stonehenge is present in topics with thematic patterns of developing education and research (Topic 4) and the summer solstice (Topic 5). Callanish is presented in the context of visitor experience to the monument as part of the landscape (Topic 2) and aligned with the significance of the site’s location (Topic 1). These variations open discussions on differences in the presentation of Neolithic sites accessible for heritage tourism between England and the Outer Hebrides. The differences in framing visitor experiences for each site further highlight what facets of these sites are presented to the public, that contribute to how they perceive past uses of the site along with how these sites fit within modern lenses of interest.

Figure 2. LDA results from the ELM platform on the heritage tourism topic

Similarly to ELM, Replit (**Figure 3**) also presented a less-generalized, continued balanced explanation for both Stonehenge (Topic 1 and Topic 5) and Callanish (Topic 2 and Topic 3) that support developed academic arguments. There was an additional slew of new terms introduced in this iteration of LDA, including: *monument*, *bluestones*, *construction*, *beauty*, *ceremonial* and *surrounding*. Responses from this platform integrated more specificity and linguistic alignment leading to ‘proof’ supporting generated information for the public. For example, the bluestones and

sarsens are now situated in a narrative rooted in the astronomical significance of Stonehenge (Topic 1) rather than presenting information regarding the movement of these stones to the landscape or construction of the site. Additionally, there is reference to the cultural significance of ancient practices that are factors contributing to current social uses of heritage and history (Topic 5). Responses from Replit also included the *why* factor, which is integral for users to gain insight and understanding into the meaning behind concepts and further supporting ‘trendy’ keywords used: *“One of Stonehenge’s most remarkable features is its alignment with the sunrise of the summer solstice and sunset of the winter solstice. This suggests its use as an ancient calendar or for ceremonial purposes related to the agricultural season (STO/ENG/Prompt 2/Response 4)”* Rather than simply mentioning the existence of the solar alignment, the responses included the depth of supporting evidence as to what this alignment could have meant for the past people who constructed and used the monument and landscape – that can increase public understanding into why this site still remains important in the current landscape. This is further seen with the additional connection of a ‘visitor experience’ at Callanish explicitly relative to surrounding sites and physical attributes within the landscape (Topic 2) and external considerations of the natural beauty and history exclusive to the Isle of Lewis (Topic 3), i.e., *“The surrounding scenery enhances the mystical and ancient ambiance of the stones... (CAL/ENG/Prompt 1/Response 8).”* The information generated within Replit included terminology reflected in typical authorised heritage discourse – specifically within critical heritage studies – visible with both Callanish and Stonehenge situated within the lens of monuments linked with physical natural aesthetics as being both valuable and integral for modern understanding.

Figure 3. LDA results from the Replit platform on the heritage tourism topic

4.2. Subject Area 2: Contested Heritage

OpenAI (**Figure 4**) emphasizes the contemporary significance and evolving narratives surrounding the Valley of the Fallen and ESMA, highlighting these sites embedding in present-day cultural and political discourses (Topics 2 and 4). Rather than treating them as static historical landmarks, the model reflects each location becoming a symbolic arena for memory, identity and public debate. For instance, one response situates the Valley of the Fallen (Valle de los Caídos, now officially the Valley of Cuelgamuros) as “*a monumental complex in Spain built after the Spanish Civil War (...) located in the Sierra de Guadarrama, about 50 km (30 miles) northwest of Madrid*”, and [having] been “*at the center of historical and political controversy for decades*” (ESP/ENG-G1-OpenAI Response 7). This description not only establishes the site’s historical and geographical context but also signals its contested nature, illustrating how the model recognises ongoing societal debates surrounding the monument. The language emphasises contemporary interpretations of justice, remembrance, and national trauma (*memory, justice, rights*), reinforcing the understanding of the site as a space where historical memory and current social values intersect. Furthermore, both the Valley of the Fallen and ESMA are framed as clear examples of contested heritage (Topic 3), reflected in the repeated references to *victims, site, war, and symbol*, which underscore the ideological and emotional tensions inherent in public engagement with these locations.

Regarding ESMA, OpenAI responses place strong emphasis on its function as a repressive instrument of state terror during the Argentine dictatorship (Topic 6). The model repeatedly associates the site with terms such as *torture, clandestine, and victims*, highlighting the systematic human rights abuses that occurred. One response states that “*ESMA is a key site where extensive human rights violations occurred. Victims of the dictatorship were detained here without due process, subjected to brutal torture, and many were murdered or disappeared*” (ARG/ENG-G1-OpenAI Response 3). This description not only situates ESMA historically but also underscores the severity and scale of the atrocities committed, reflecting the site’s centrality in narratives of state repression and human rights violations. In addition, the responses acknowledge ESMA’s later transformation into a memorial and educational space (Topic 4), emphasising its ongoing role in promoting truth, justice, and reparative memory, with repeated references to *museum, heritage, justice, and rights*. This framing positions ESMA as both a site of historical trauma and a locus for contemporary memory work, illustrating the dual significance of the site in Argentine society.

Figure 4. LDA results for the Open AI platform on the contested heritage topic.

In contrast, ELM (**Figure 5**) engages more directly with the core issues and controversies that define the contemporary significance of the Valley of the Fallen and ESMA (Topics 2, 3, 5, 6, and 7). The model elucidates key tensions, including the construction process (*forced, labor, prisoners*) and ongoing democratic reinterpretations salient with the Valley of the Fallen, where debates persist around its original Francoist symbolism and potential democratic reframing (*exhumation, consent, democratic*). Equally, ELM captured contentious discourse surrounding the number of disappeared victims at ESMA in Topic 3 (*estimated, disappeared, bodies*), a remaining politically charged issue in Argentina and central to the site’s contested legacy. In this context, one response notes that “*it is estimated that around 5,000 people were detained and disappeared at the ESMA, though the exact number of deaths is not precisely known. Many of the detainees were victims of forced disappearance, and their bodies were never recovered*” (ARG/ENG-S1-ELM Response 1). This description highlights both the scale of the abuses and the enduring uncertainties surrounding the historical record, underscoring why ESMA remains a highly charged and symbolically significant location.

Beyond recognizing the plurality of these sites' meanings and values (Topics 1–2), the model reflects a lexical alignment with memory politics, social justice and democratic values (*historical, memory, victims, human, rights, democratic*). This suggests an awareness of broader social debates

and engagement with the cultural and political dimensions of heritage. The Valley of the Fallen is described as a site where “*thousands of combatants from both sides of the war are buried there, including many Republicans interred without their families' consent. This has been a source of pain and controversy, sparking calls for the exhumation and return of these remains to their families*” (ESP/ENG-G2-ELM Response 1). This framing highlights the ongoing ethical and social debates surrounding the treatment of the dead and the contested legacy of the site. Similarly, the same response notes the site’s role in contemporary historical memory discussions: “*The site has become central in Spain’s ongoing debate over how to deal with its history of the Civil War and the Francoist regime. The Law of Historical Memory and the more recent Law of Democratic Memory aim to address these issues, impacting how the site is respected and curated*” (ESP/ENG-S1-ELM Response 1). Together, these statements present the Valley of the Fallen not as a static historical or commemorative space but as an active arena where memory, identity, and power intersect and evolve in response to public discourse and social demand.

Figure 5. LDA results for the ELM platform on the contested heritage topic.

Similarly, in Topics 1, 2, and 6, Replit responses (**Figure 6**) demonstrate a strong capacity to identify underlying values and symbolic meanings associated with the Valley of the Fallen and ESMA. The platform consistently frames these locations as examples of contested heritage (Topics 3 and 6; *memorial, legacy, place*), recognising their complex historical legacies and the tensions surrounding interpretation and public use. Regarding ESMA, Replit highlights the site’s repressive role during the Argentine dictatorship (Topic 7), noting its function within the state terror system

and its centrality in contemporary memory politics through references to terms such as *clandestine*, *number*, *disappeared*, *human*, and *rights*. The responses also address key contemporary controversies, including issues of legitimacy, memory, and victimhood (*complex*, *atrocities*, *prisoners*). However, in contrast to ELM, Replit exhibits a higher frequency of relevant terms, reflecting strong lexical engagement while maintaining a neutral or largely apolitical tone. As one response explains, the Valley of the Fallen is “*a monumental complex located in the Sierra de Guadarrama, near Madrid (...) built between 1940 and 1959, during Francisco Franco's dictatorship*” and “*partly with the labor of political prisoners*” (ESP/ENG-G1-Replit Response 4). This situates the site both historically and politically, emphasising its contentious legacy as a Francoist monument while noting its intended function as a memorial for those who died during the Spanish Civil War.

Similarly, the ESMA is described as “*one of the most notorious clandestine detention, torture, and extermination centers used during Argentina's Dirty War (1976–1983)*” where “*around 5,000 people were held (...) many of whom were tortured and ultimately ‘disappeared’*” and “*a significant number of the detainees were killed. The site is now a museum and a memorial to the victims of the dictatorship*” (ARG/ENG-S1-Replit Response 6). This description highlights both the systematic human rights abuses that occurred and the site’s contemporary function as a space of memory and education, underscoring its continued significance in Argentine society. Overall, Replit presents both the Valley of the Fallen and ESMA in a descriptive, information-focused manner, marking a subtle but important shift in emphasis compared to ELM: while identifying similar core issues, the responses are less explicitly value-driven, offering an informative and restrained framing of contested heritage.

Figure 6. LDA results for the Replit platform on the contested heritage topic.

5. Discussion

This paper provides an exploratory study into the variability of responses generated by a singular generative AI model between different platforms. Even with the exploratory nature of this study, results and interpretations are valuable for developing future research using alternative quantitative analyses applied to larger corpuses, along with uncovering limitations within this study and additional questions. We aimed to demonstrate the intricate and often inconsistent nature of generated responses, but with variability linked to platforms that could influence users – both their experience with the platform itself and understanding archaeological heritage subjects. In evaluating how heritage knowledge is generated across each platform, results uncovered that while the model – ChatGPT-4o – remains the same, narratives differ according to the selected platform.

Within this exploratory framework, topic modelling (LDA) was used primarily as a heuristic tool to identify thematic tendencies and assess whether the dataset exhibited sufficient inter-platform variability to justify deeper quantitative investigation. The aim was not to produce a definitive quantitative comparison between platforms, but rather to use topic patterns as an initial indicator of differences in narrative framing and thematic emphasis. Accordingly, while LDA outputs informed the analysis, the interpretations presented here remain largely qualitative and are discussed in relation to existing theoretical perspectives on platform mediation and knowledge production. These methodological choices also introduce limitations. In particular, cross-platform comparison was not implemented through a single unified LDA model applied to the entire corpus. Instead,

topic modelling was used to explore thematic tendencies within the dataset. Although a combined LDA could provide a more formal quantitative comparison, our approach was intended to determine whether observable differences between platforms warrant a more comprehensive quantitative study. Therefore, the results should be interpreted as exploratory indicators rather than definitive statistical comparisons.

Focusing first on the differences, contextual framing of the chosen sites can be linked to varying academic and public perceptions and usage of archaeological heritage – notably in the presented subject areas of heritage tourism and contested heritage. Examining each platform as its own case study provided insight and clarity into platform-specific presentations of archaeological heritage knowledge that can influence users’ future engagement with tourism practices and contestations. Beyond the context and narrative of the information provided, it was also possible to evaluate the platforms themselves following our classification scheme discussed above. We recognize the limitations these choices had on our analyses, specifically impacting LDA cross-platform comparison and intra-platform variability. Ultimately, there are distinct ‘platform experiences’, in which each platform provides users with a particular narrative that contributes to shaping public understanding of tourism and memory heritage. Our goal was to demonstrate that sufficient variability exists between platforms not only to highlight implications for user experience –both in terms of platform use and the information generated– but also to motivate larger-scale studies into platform mediation in generative AI systems. However, it is important to reiterate that these platforms operate as black-box systems, meaning that underlying parameters, system prompts, and model configurations remain inaccessible to users and researchers. As such, this represents a methodological limitation that cannot be controlled within the scope of this study, in contrast to experimental settings where variables such as test conditions or model design can be systematically manipulated. Nevertheless, thematic patterns, recurring ‘buzzwords’, and shifting contextual framings were observable across the generated responses, suggesting that platform-level mediation may play a role in shaping the narratives presented to users and warranting further systematic evaluation.

Beginning with Subject Area 1: Heritage Tourism, generated responses and the LDA models were interpreted in line with both a critical heritage studies perspective and the classification scheme – to unveil the variability of narratives and contexts within presented information. Focusing on the sites of Stonehenge and Callanish, it was possible to interpret results using current trends and debates within research to better comment on the responses. Each of the three platforms were capable of recognizing concepts and characteristics of heritage tourism that permeates research. OpenAI produced the most generalized and vague surface-level explanations situated in Stonehenge-centric narratives – resulting in easily-comprehensible responses for all users, evidenced by a lack of intricate details. Both ELM and Replit supplied more specific accounts of contextual framing found in current heritage tourism discussions – academically and publicly – reflected in expert-level terms and emerging embodied interpretations. The narratives for both are more balanced between the two sites, with ELM containing more UK-centric, academic terminology and Replit

providing a broader, yet still technical explanation. While each of the platforms are capable of providing users with heritage tourism knowledge – said knowledge does vary in complexity, accessibility and type of information presented.

The responses from OpenAI – brief, shallow explanations and Stonehenge-focused – illustrate an underlying dominant narrative of Stonehenge, potentially reinforcing known biases in academic research and tourism practices. For example, Prompt 1 (*i.e.*, “*Tell me about Callanish – what to see, features, and best time to visit*”) pertains to Callanish, yet ‘Stonehenge’ is referenced – unprompted – in all 15 responses. Though, in prompts exclusive to Stonehenge – there were no references or explicit mentions of Callanish. This reflects how in many instances, Stonehenge and Callanish are not granted the same agency of significance, meaning or in some cases types of value leading to a hierarchy of perception into each of these sites. Generalized responses are bolstered by ‘trendy’ keywords, while lacking depth in connecting these terms with *why* certain aspects and physical features are still important today. Stonehenge is considered iconic and mysterious but *why*? Making a claim about the ‘solstice alignment’ or use by modern druids does not provide a user with the meaning behind this referencing. This can further impact the users understanding of the past – specifically interpretations and observations into potential uses of these sites – with responses contributing to influencing perceptions and potential engagements with heritage tourism practices. Ultimately, the OpenAI platform is capable of providing users with an overview and answers to their prompts yet the narrative framing of responses indicate an inability to provide a depth of responses that account for critical perspectives and interpretations. All responses investigated in this study were the result of a single prompt – so it is fair to acknowledge that responses of OpenAI could lead to depth with continued prompting. What is interesting is the variation of responses – thematic patterns and context – limited to single prompts.

While there is a thematic overlap between the OpenAI platform, the ELM topics were less vague and contained clearer terms presenting site locations and characteristics in line with tourism interpretations. Responses were also less Stonehenge-centric, out of all of the 15 responses for Prompt 1 in ELM – there were only four references of Stonehenge. The ELM platform maintained a more balanced presentation of the respective sites in generated responses. Narratives reiterated current trends in archaeological heritage research – considering the importance of the monument existing as part of the landscape, rather than separate and inclusion of various heritage value-types. These research directions are clear within studies on heritage education, visitor experience and landscape archaeology. Important to note is that responses from ELM further align with the concept of heritagescapes (Garden 2006) within current discourse, that emphasize surviving monuments as dynamic rather than static. That through the lens of heritage tourism specifically (Burlingame 2022), that by having an embodied interpretation of a site as layered to include the monument, surrounding landscape and nearby sites showcases the full extent of these spaces impacting tourism practices and visitor experiences (Karagöz & Ramkissoon 2025). The presence of this concept was discernible in the increased terminology relative to surrounding sites, the

physical landscape and terminology that is recognised within ongoing authorised heritage discourse.

Similar to ELM, Replit responses were more balanced between both sites while also providing depth within said responses, providing users with meaning and evidence to support claims. For example, considering the role of ‘heritage tourism’ the subject itself appeared within responses. Looking at prompt 4 (i.e., “*Is Stonehenge still relevant today and is its use case still viable for our modern society?*”) one of the OpenAI responses was, “*But as a cultural artifact and tourism draw? Still incredibly valuable. (STO/ENG/Prompt 4/Response 8).*” While the information generated does highlight Stonehenge as maintaining a ‘tourism draw’ linked with value within the modern landscape, the response is sparse regarding providing users the ‘why’ that better guides connection. Whereas, within Replit, the same prompt resulted in, “*Stonehenge attracts millions of visitors from around the world every year, contributing to the local and national economy. Its iconic status makes it a must-visit location for many tourists interested in history and ancient cultures (STO/ENG/Prompt4/Response 9).*” Here, the information is placed in a clear context for users to understand what factors (i.e., financial, culture, etc.) drive interest in the site, along with outcomes of visiting Stonehenge. This variability in depth, meaning and social uses of these aspects of the past in the present can potentially influence user perception on the role of heritage tourism in general, while also impacting public understanding of the value behind visiting these sites.

In the analysis of Subject Area 2: Contested Heritage, all three models – OpenAI, ELM, and Replit – successfully identify central themes and values associated with the Valley of the Fallen and ESMA. Each system recognises that these sites are embedded within broader historical and political debates and highlights their connections to collective memory, historical trauma, and processes of public interpretation. In this respect, the models demonstrate a general capacity to detect the key elements that typically frame discussions of controversial or politically sensitive heritage sites.

However, the platforms differ significantly in terms of linguistic complexity, as well as the type and depth of information conveyed. ELM produces the most complex and academically nuanced responses, frequently employing specialised terminology and implicitly drawing on conceptual frameworks commonly associated with heritage studies, memory politics, and transitional justice. For example, when discussing the Valley of the Fallen, ELM explicitly situates the monument within ongoing legislation and debates about historical interpretation, noting that “*The monument is at the center of ongoing debates on how Spain should confront its Civil War and Francoist past. The Historical Memory Law and Democratic Memory Law aim to address these issues, emphasizing the need for a more inclusive and accurate historical narrative*” (ESP/ENG-G2-ELM Response 2). Similarly, in the case of ESMA, ELM foregrounds the site’s educational and commemorative function by explicitly invoking the framework of “memory, truth, and justice”. As one response states, “*The museum honors the victims and educates the public about human rights through exhibitions and activities focused on memory, truth, and justice*” (ARG/ENG-G1-ELM

Response 12). By framing the site in these terms, ELM situates ESMA within broader discussions surrounding democratic values, historical accountability, and the institutionalisation of memory in post-authoritarian societies. This style of response reflects a more academically inflected discourse, resembling the language commonly found in heritage and memory studies, and implicitly assumes a degree of prior contextual knowledge on the part of the reader.

Replit, by contrast, effectively captures the core issues and recurring patterns that characterise contested heritage, including political symbolism, historical reinterpretation, and public disagreement over the meaning of memorial sites. Nevertheless, these themes are typically presented in a more neutral and less overtly politicised tone. For instance, when discussing ESMA, Replit frames the site primarily in terms of historical transformation, stating that “*The transition of the ESMA from a site of terror to a space of memory is symbolic of Argentina's broader efforts to confront and reconcile with its past*” (ARG/ENG-G1-Replit Response 3). Likewise, its descriptions often prioritise architectural or factual information. In its explanation of the Valley of the Fallen, for example, the model highlights the monument’s physical characteristics and historical associations: “*The monument is notable for its basilica carved into a mountainside and the massive cross above the basilica, which stands about 150 meters tall and is one of the tallest in the world. The site was formerly the burial place of Francisco Franco, whose remains were interred there until their exhumation in 2019. It also holds the remains of José Antonio Primo de Rivera, founder of the Falange, a fascist political organization*” (ESP/ENG-G1-Replit Response 6). This approach conveys the essential historical and contextual information while avoiding extensive engagement with interpretative controversies, resulting in responses that are informative yet comparatively restrained in analytical depth.

OpenAI provides the most limited informational scope among the three systems. Its responses are generally structured using simpler language and broader explanations, prioritising clarity and readability over conceptual complexity. For example, when describing the Valley of the Fallen, the model emphasises the monument’s controversial status, noting that “*The Valley of the Fallen (Valle de los Caídos, now officially the Valley of Cuelgamuros) is one of the most controversial monuments in Spain, and possibly in Europe. Built during the Francoist dictatorship, it was meant to commemorate those who died in the Spanish Civil War (1936–1939), but its meaning, symbolism, and legacy have sparked intense debate, pain, and political division*” (ESP/ENG-S1-Open AI Response 5). In the case of ESMA, the model similarly provides a concise historical overview, stating that “*The ESMA (Escuela de Mecánica de la Armada), one of the most infamous clandestine detention, torture, and extermination centers during Argentina's Dirty War (1976–1983), is estimated to have been responsible for the deaths of around 5,000 people*” (ARG/ENG-S1-Open AI Response 6). While such formulations make the information accessible to a broad audience, they engage less extensively with the wider societal, political, and historiographical debates surrounding these sites. Consequently, although the model clearly recognises the contested nature of the sites, it engages less deeply with the interpretative layers and ongoing public discussions that shape these memoryscapes.

For both of the subject areas differences between each platform – as to the degree of clearly identifying terms and interpretations in the heritage context – showcase why this line of questioning is necessary regarding the use of generative AI models. Different generative AI models, beyond ChatGPT-4o, have been previously explored to better understand levels of authenticity, credibility, reliability and transparency of generated responses – yet the same assessment needs to be redirected to how these models are accessed. We decided to focus on the complexity, accessibility and type of information each platform produces as a classification scheme and interpretation tool. To gain insight into the advantages some platforms afforded to users over others, and disadvantages. Utilizing the framing of the three classifiers introduced above and interpretations from our exploratory analysis, we have a preliminary overview of how each platform situated (**Table 5**). An aspect we wish to comment on – in early stages – is the potential detriment that these emergent technologies could saturate modern information-seeking practices while replicating existing knowledge hierarchies. Current variabilities and interpretations have ‘prompted’ the authors to consider the impact of the variability on democratising – or monopolizing – knowledge in the heritage sphere. Future explorations can account for limitations and provide a more robust quantitative analysis.

	OpenAI	ELM	Replit
Accessibility	Option for either a free account or paid account (with registration) User-friendly online interface	Restricted access (limited to University of Edinburgh students and staff) User-friendly online interface	Free access (with registration and using an API key) Access to ChatGPT-4o via online interface
Complexity	User-friendly (intended for the general public) No Digital Literacy required	User-friendly (classified as a ‘learning tool’) No Digital Literacy required	Necessary to run code in the Python language to prompt ChatGPT 4o Digital Literacy required (familiarity with APIs and programming languages)
Type of info	Basic and general information	Academic and curated responses	Brief and specific information

Table 5. OpenAI, ELM and Replit characteristics based on the accessibility, the complexity and the type of information presented by these platforms.

Table 5 summarises the main characteristics of the three platforms analysed –OpenAI, ELM and Replit– according to three key dimensions: accessibility, operational complexity, and the type of information typically produced. These classifications provide a useful framework for interpreting the differences observed in the generated responses.

Accessing ChatGPT-4o through the OpenAI platform –particularly through its free option– significantly increases accessibility to the chatbot. The platform offers a user-friendly online interface and does not require advanced digital literacy, making it suitable for a broad audience, including users with little or no technical background. In terms of complexity, OpenAI is designed for general use, prioritising ease of interaction over technical sophistication. The type of information it produces tends to be basic and general, providing a clear and accessible overview of topics rather than in-depth or academically curated content. The combination of high accessibility, low operational complexity, and simplified informational output makes OpenAI a powerful tool for democratising knowledge and providing rapid, inclusive access to generative AI, even if it occasionally does so at the expense of depth or specialised precision.

This expansion of access, however, comes with trade-offs. While users gain unprecedented reach and convenience, the outputs may lack the methodological rigour or analytical framing that characterises more academically oriented tools. Nevertheless, for many practical purposes –such as preliminary research, introductory learning, or rapid information retrieval– the benefits of accessibility and usability may outweigh these limitations, particularly in contexts where speed, inclusivity, and engagement are prioritised over exhaustive accuracy.

By contrast, platforms such as ELM and Replit present higher barriers to entry. ELM, for example, typically requires institutional affiliation, restricting access primarily to students and staff at the University of Edinburgh. Despite this limitation, the platform remains user-friendly and does not demand specialised technical skills. Its operational complexity is moderate: the system functions as a ‘learning tool’ that guides users through structured prompts rather than requiring programming knowledge. The type of information produced is academic and curated, often methodologically rigorous and well-suited to scholarly or research-focused applications. This combination of controlled access, moderate complexity, and curated outputs makes ELM particularly valuable for tasks requiring reliable, high-quality, and contextually nuanced information.

Replit represents the most technically demanding environment of the three platforms. Interacting with ChatGPT-4o via Replit generally requires users to run code –commonly in Python– and to manage API interactions to prompt the model. This necessitates a higher level of digital literacy and familiarity with programming languages. In terms of complexity, Replit is therefore the most sophisticated platform, offering flexibility and advanced functionality but limiting accessibility for non-technical users. The information it produces is typically brief and specific, oriented toward technical experimentation and development rather than general public engagement. Users with the

necessary expertise can exploit these features for customised and precise model interactions, but those without programming experience may find the platform challenging to navigate.

In sum, the three platforms occupy distinct positions across the dimensions of accessibility, complexity, and informational type: OpenAI maximises accessibility and simplicity at the cost of depth; ELM balances controlled access with academically rigorous outputs; and Replit prioritises technical flexibility and specificity, requiring higher digital literacy for effective use.

This disparity raises critical concerns, in which we began considering equity and inclusion. If the most reliable and sophisticated generative AI tools are only accessible to those with advanced educational or technical credentials, there is a genuine risk of reinforcing – rather than narrowing – existing digital and educational divides. These challenges are particularly acute in socially resonant domains such as heritage tourism or memorial sites, where the limitations and biases of different platforms can significantly shape users’ experiences and perceptions. The presentation of information – the narratives and contexts – provide the lens through which users gain understanding into the discussed subject areas, further emphasizing the need to evaluate any presence within generative AI. In this context, it will be particularly important to assess the impact of the forthcoming European AI Act (Regulation (EU) 2024/1689), which, set to come into force in August 2026, requires the publication of summaries outlining the data used for model training. Since GPT-5 was released prior to these regulations, we will need to await the next iteration to determine whether these measures lead to a meaningful shift in transparency, accessibility, and the mitigation of biases in generative AI.

6. Conclusion

Continuously increasing access to generative AI across the digital landscape has resulted in a plethora of research throughout various disciplines grounded in understanding the benefits and shortcomings of utilising these models. The above exploratory study aimed to contribute to growing debates on the integration of these models within the archaeological heritage context, through the lens of ‘platform experiences’ impacting public perception of heritage tourism and contested heritage. The concerns outlined above centred on issues related to complexity, accessibility and type of information – as an interpretive lens through which to view both platforms and responses. The overall goal was to establish a baseline – of questioning, exploring the interpretive lens and gaining insight in response variability between platforms. To ultimately use this study to see the potential of expanding into large-scale explorations of potential ‘knowledge hierarchies’ that could have an impact on the future pedagogical role of these models.

While these technologies are often promoted as widely available and user-friendly, previous research and this study reveals layers inequalities shaped by socio-technical (Kruglikova 2024), linguistic (González Cantera & Bonacchi 2025) and educational barriers (Bodani *et al.* 2023). Over the past two decades, scholars have critically examined the level that digital technologies have genuinely “democratised” access to heritage, as well as their influence over decision-making

processes concerning which aspects of the past are valued, narrated and preserved (Terren 2022; Hu 2023). Rather than dismantling traditional hierarchies, some argue that digitisation may reinforce dominant interpretations of the past, often framed through Authorised Heritage Discourses (Hu 2023). Similarly, others have drawn attention to the tendency of social media and digital platforms amplifying hegemonic narratives, marginalising alternative perspectives (Taylor & Gibson 2017). Accounting for these longstanding concerns in conjunction with the preliminary results gleaned from the above exploration – we want to leave readers with the final consideration of the emerging issue of unequal access to the platforms through which generative AI models, such as ChatGPT-4o is deployed.

While the model itself is theoretically open to the public, in practice, the most academically robust and coherent outputs tend to be generated through non-universally accessible interfaces. For instance, platforms such as ELM require institutional affiliation, typically tied to higher education, while others, such as Replit, do require technical competence, knowledge of programming languages like Python and a level of comfort using this type of interface. The type of discrepancies that arose – length of responses, narrative patterns – raised more questions about the extent to which generative AI models could be active participants in reinforcing existing inequalities in access to knowledge. Even now, users are able to prompt the newest ChatGPT model five times before having access restricted for hours – unless you want to pay. ELM could be a great, enriching tool – until a student graduates from the University of Edinburgh. If these platforms privilege users with specific educational or technical backgrounds, does this not risk reproducing or even deepening the digital and educational divide? Time, and future large-scale explorations can highlight the extent to which these concerns are currently manifesting in the digital landscape.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors report that there are no conflicts of interest surrounding the research presented in this paper. The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest in relation to the content of the article.

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